

Community health profile in Barangay Pantihan II at Maragondon, Cavite, Philippines as an adopted community of St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

This paper assessed the community health profile of family members in Barangay Pantihan II at Maragondon, Cavite, Philippines. The paper aimed to analyze the health status and evaluate the health resources, services and systems of care within the community. One hundred and sixty-five (165) families with an overall number of 760 members in the household participated in the study. Using a community health needs assessment, the students were immersed in the community for nine days. Frequencies and percentages were used to determine the status of the households at Barangay Pantihan II in Maragondon, Cavite. Results discovered about disposals, birth deliveries, adequacies, illnesses, and other functions which can be related or connected in their respective households. Barangay leaders and stakeholders from St. Dominic College of Asia must plan and implement steps to address the needs and problems of community, particularly in a specific barangay.

Keywords: *Community health assessment; Barangay Pantihan II; Maragondon, Cavite; Adopted community.*

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Introduction

We, as individuals and as members of our own families, are also members of a community. A community is composed of different types of people, but they are united by similar objectives, which are to improve and progress their own community. Each individual in the community is interacting in order to improve their sedentary lifestyle and be able to perform at their optimum level of functioning. The members function to help one another grow and be mature enough to deal with life challenges.

People are the building blocks of the community; they need one another in order to function effectively. Through constant communication, they are ready to meet the crisis that will arise in their community. Also, they will be aware of the entry of new members who will participate in their community affairs. A community with a good foundation can develop a sense of maturity and an ideal lifestyle that will best benefit each member. Moreover, individuals in the community have the capacity to improve their health and prevent various diseases from occurring. Through channels, people can seek health information, which is an effective way to begin preparing for and accepting specific problems that will arise in their community.

According to Perry et al. (2014), community health workers can be efficient in promoting population health in different countries, regardless of income. Although they can be temporary solutions, CHWs should be part of health systems that include formal health programs, communities, and specific interventions for their outreach delivery. Similarly, Kok et al. (2016) said that their contribution has been made possible in achieving health goals through various programs such as community selection, monitoring, and support.

On the other hand, Jaskiewicz and Tulenko (2012) cited that the productivity of CHWs is influenced by several elements such as workload, supportive supervision, supplies and equipment, and respect that could help them to do their professions more effectively based on good working conditions. Another study by Van Iersel et al. (2016) suggested that community care does not only involve health workers, particularly those from the nursing field, but also the students themselves, who work autonomously on small, different tasks, providing care for patients. Therefore, a challenging and attractive alternative must be made so that students may be encouraged to choose community healthcare nursing as their future profession.

In the Philippines, barangay health workers play an essential role in their motivations for volunteering in different activities and programs (Mallari et al., 2020; Haw et al., 2016). Despite the lack of incentives towards them, they still have established camaraderie among other BHWs, patients, and the community, as well as the knowledge and skills they have learned in the program. Some medicine graduates may opt to continue as rural health physicians in local government units or become medical officers in provincial hospitals; however, it is important that health professional education be integrated with community health needs through strong partnerships between health education, health sectors, and rural communities (Siega-Sur et al., 2017).

In the course of our study, we will focus our attention on improving their socialization with each member by conducting activities that will give them the chance to communicate and share common desires for the wellness of their community. The development of the physical features is supported by each individual and fights for the inevitable changes in health. Instructing people to visit health centers and recognize the importance of health is helpful for achieving a successful community. Providing each individual with adequate knowledge with which they can sustain an optimal level of health.

As competitive student nurses, they play a significant role in the progress of the community. Their goals are for the benefit of each member, and they aspire for positive changes that will facilitate a healthy lifestyle through community health programs. Constant participation from individuals will also help them update their clinical skills and strategies to initiate changes. As in the study of Querri et al. (2020), since the conduct of community profiling was not considered one of the roles of community health workers based on the needs of the people, trainings are also given to boost their responsibility in promoting more responsive health services in primary health care.

Community health nurses need to know the defining characteristics of a community because these could “set” the stage for understanding the different aspects that directly or indirectly influence the health status of the community (Scott et al., 2018; Stanhope & Lancaster, 2019). In respect to this, the researchers conducted a community health assessment (otherwise known as a community diagnosis) at Brgy. Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite, in order to develop a community-based, community-owned process to:

- Analyze the health status of at Brgy. Pantihan II of Maragondon community.
- Evaluate the health resources, services and systems of care within the community.
- Assess the community’s attitude towards community health services and issues.
- Identify priorities, establish goals and determine a course of action to improve the health status of the community.
- Establish a baseline for measuring improvement of the community overtime.

Objectives of the Study

By the end of the nine days of community exposure, the community will be knowledgeable and aware of their present health condition and other community problems and provide necessary action and solutions to the prioritized problems. Specifically, it offers the following goals:

1. Establish rapport with the barangay officials and community people throughout the community exposure.
2. Gather relevant data through community survey and observation regarding socio-economic and socio-demographic of the barangay.
3. Evaluate health resources, services, and systems of care within the community.
4. Assess attitudes toward community health services and issues.
5. Analyze and interpret data and produce a comprehensive output that shows the barangay's present condition in terms of social, economic, political and health aspects.
6. Determine problems, needs of the community, and identify what problems should be prioritized and need immediate attention.
7. Construct a timely and appropriate problem tree for the prioritized problem of the community taking into considerations the community's available resources.
8. Help the community people in formulating resolutions that best addressed the identified problems of the barangay.
9. Empower the people in maximizing the available community resources and produce programs that will aid in continued community development and progress.

Methodology

The Municipality of Maragondon is a third-class municipality in the province of Cavite, Philippines. Maragondon is 54 kilometers (34 mi) south-west of Manila. According to the 2015 census, it has a population of 37,720 people (Provincial Government of Cavite, n.d.). Out of 27 barangays, Pantihan II was selected to be the adopted community of St. Dominic College of Asia, according to the researchers. The researchers conducted a community health assessment survey, which served as the basis for the fourth-year nursing students of St. Dominic College of Asia, to identify the different factors that directly and indirectly affect the health of the people who are residing in Barangay Pantihan II.

One hundred and sixty-five (165) families with an overall number of 760 members in the household participated in the study. The students were immersed in the community for nine days. During the said exposure, the students are bound to gather data, and all supporting details and analyze them for the final paper. In gathering the data, the students conveniently selected their respondents; they conducted surveys using the questionnaires about the family assessment guide given and conceptualized by the St. Dominic College of Asia's Community Extension Services Office. The students, as well, spent two hours in the field and two hours in the health center. Frequencies and percentages were used to determine the status of the households at Barangay Pantihan II in Maragondon, Cavite.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Percentage Distribution Showing Age Distribution of Surveyed Households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 760)

Age	Frequency	Percentage
0-12 months	15	1.97%
1-3 years old	31	4.08%
4-6 years old	54	7.11%
7-12 years old	108	14.21%
13-19 years old	119	15.66%
20-40 years old	278	36.58%
41-59 years old	112	14.74%
60 years old and above	43	5.66%

The table presents the distribution of respondents in terms of family age. In a total of seven hundred sixty (760) respondents, there are fifteen (15) from zero (0) to 12 months old, thirty-one (31) from one (1) to three (3) years old, fifty-four (54) from four (4) to six (6) years old, one hundred eight (108) from seven (7) to 12 years old, one hundred nineteen (119) from 13 to 19 years old, two hundred seventy eight (278) from 20 to 40 years old, one hundred twelve (112) from 41 to 59 years old, and forty-three (43) from 60 years old and above. Results showed that most participants were aged from 20 to 40 years old.

Table 2. Percentage Distribution Showing Gender Distribution of Surveyed Households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 760)

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	369	48.55%
Female	382	50.26%

The computation shows that 51% or 382 residents were females and 49% or 369 were males in Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite. This resulted that more participants were females than males.

Table 3. Percentage Distribution Showing Careers of Surveyed Households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 760)

Career	Frequency	Percentage
Business and Finance	74	9.74%
Agriculture	44	5.79%
Transportation	34	4.47%
Architecture and Construction	18	2.37%
Sales and Marketing	17	2.24%
Education	12	1.58%
Healthcare and Medicine	10	1.32%
OFW	8	1.05%
Military	7	0.92%
Information Technology	6	0.79%
Engineering	5	0.66%
Housekeeping	4	0.53%
Cosmetology	1	0.13%
Student	53	6.97%
Unemployed	461	60.66%

The table presents the percentage distribution showing careers of surveyed households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite. In this table, 74 or 9.74% of the respondents were working in business and finance, while some were students with a total of 53 or 6.97% of the population. Others were employed with the following: agriculture (5.79%), transportation (4.47%), architecture and construction (2.37%), sales and marketing (2.24%), healthcare and medicine (1.32%), overseas Filipino work (1.05%), military (0.92%), information technology (0.79%), engineering (0.66%), housekeeping (0.53%), and cosmetology (0.13%). It is also evident that more respondents are still unemployed with a total of 461 or 60.66% of the respondents. Brand (2015) said that job displacement causes dramatic changes in the progressions of workers which result in unemployment and allows for reliable estimations of the relationships between socioeconomic conditions and life outcomes which can be associated to the economic decline of a certain nation. Employment growth has yet to increase the economic status of a community which would help enhance the domestic demands for goods and services.

Table 4. Percentage Distribution Showing Educational Background of Surveyed Households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 760)

Educational Background	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary Undergraduate	118	15.53%
Elementary Graduate	83	10.92%
High School Undergraduate	102	13.42%
High School Graduate	172	22.63%
College Undergraduate	49	6.45%
College Graduate	119	15.66%
Vocational	81	10.66%
Postgraduate	23	3.03%
Never	13	1.71%

The table shows the distribution of the educational background among family members where the highest number of participants were high school graduates with 22.63% or 172; the next ones were college graduates with 15.65% or 119, followed by elementary graduates with 15.52% or 118, then high school undergraduates with 13.42% or 102; next to that were elementary graduates with 10.92% or 83. Some also finished under a vocational program with 10.65% or 81 of the participants, as well as college undergraduates with 6.44% or 59 and post graduates with 3.02% or 23. The last ones that never got a chance to go to school are with 1.71% or 13 respondents. Results showed that most of the respondents were high school graduates, implying that either they have finished high school and are planning to go to college, or have decided not to go to college for their personal opportunities.

Table 5. Percentage Distribution Showing Religion of Surveyed Households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 165)

Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Catholic	149	90.30%
Born Again Christian	9	5.45%
Iglesia ni Cristo	2	1.21%
Others	5	3.03%

The graph shows the distribution of respondents in terms of religion. In one hundred sixty-five family respondents, there are one hundred forty-nine (149) Catholic, nine (9) born again Christian, three (3) Iglesia ni Cristo (INC), and five (5) others. Results indicated that most of the families at Barangay Pantihan were Roman Catholics, in which they continue to adopt more values and practices relating to their spiritual lives.

Table 6. Percentage Distribution Showing Place of Origin of Surveyed Households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 165)

Place of Origin	Frequency	Percentage
Metro Manila (National Capital Region)	8	4.85%
Region 1 (Ilocos Region)	1	0.61%
Region 3 (Central Luzon)	3	1.82%
Region 4A (CALABARZON)	132	80.00%
Region 4B (MIMAROPA)	2	1.21%
Region 5 (Bicol Region)	8	4.85%
Region 6 (Western Visayas)	3	1.82%
Region 7 (Central Visayas)	1	0.61%
Region 8 (Eastern Visayas)	5	3.03%
Region 10 (Northern Mindanao)	1	0.61%
Region 13 (Caraga Region)	1	0.61%

The table shows the distribution of respondents in terms of place of origin. In one hundred sixty-five respondents (165), majority of the families were from Region 4A (CALABARZON) with a total of 132 or 80%, which also suggests that most came from Cavite. Eight or 4.85% of the families were also originated from Metro Manila (National Capital Region) and Region 5 (Bicol Region), respectively. Each of the families also lived in Region 1 (Ilocos Region), Region 7 (Central Visayas), Region 10 (Northern Mindanao), and Region 13 (Caraga Region). This shows that the families are more diverse in their cultures prior to moving to Barangay Pantihan II.

Table 7. Percentage Distribution Showing Length of Residence of Surveyed Households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 165)

Length of Residence	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years	23	13.94%
6-12 years	18	10.91%
13-20 years	18	10.91%
21 years and above	94	56.97%
Not applicable	12	7.27%

The table shows the distribution of respondents in terms of length of residence. In one hundred sixty-five family respondents (165) there are twenty three (23) residing for one to five years, eighteen (18) residing for six to 12 years, eighteen (18) residing for 13 to 20 years, ninety-four (94) residing for 21 years and above, and twelve (12) answered not applicable. Results indicated that most of the family respondents were living in Barangay Pantihan II for more than 20 years, implying that they have used to the cultural beliefs in their community.

Table 8. Percentage Distribution Showing Satisfaction with Communication / Transportation of Surveyed Households of Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 165)

Communication / Transportation	Frequency	Percentage
Convenient	108	65.45%
Inconvenient	57	34.55%

One hundred eight (108) or 65.45% of the respondents are satisfied and convenient with the communication and transportation on their area, while the other 57 or 34.55% are having difficult experiences on their transportation and communications. This result can be attributed with Abenoza et al. (2017) by which public transport users are more satisfied than rural motorist commuters in traveling across the board.

Table 9. Type of family (n = 165)

Type of family	Frequency	Percentage
Nuclear	116	70.30%
Extended	49	29.70%

It shows in the table that 70% or 116 of the residents of the Barangay Pantihan II in Maragondon, Cavite has a nuclear family which consists only the father, the mother, and the children. While the 30% or 49 of the residents are extended which consists of the nuclear family with their grandmothers, cousins, or living with other relatives. This shows that more families were nuclear, implying that they are more comfortable in dealing with their respective responsibilities at homes.

Table 10. Frequency Distribution Showing the Monthly Income of the Surveyed Families in Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite (n = 165)

Monthly Income	Father		Mother		Others	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 5,000	59	35.76%	75	45.45%	22	13.33%
5,001-10,000	36	21.82%	9	5.45%	12	7.27%
10,001-20,000	14	8.48%	3	1.82%	7	4.24%
20,001-30,000	5	3.03%	1	0.61%	5	3.03%
30,001 and above	2	1.21%	0	0.00%	2	1.21%
None	49	29.70%	77	46.67%	117	70.91%

The table shows that 35.76% of the fathers from the total families surveyed, which comprises of the 59 families in Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite, have a monthly income of PHP 5,000 and below. Second is the 21.81% of fathers from the total families surveyed, which comprises 36 families with an approximate monthly income of PHP 5,001–10,000. Third are the 8.49% of the fathers from the total families surveyed, which comprises 14 families with an approximate monthly income of PHP 10,001–20,000. Fourth, 3.03% of the fathers in the total families surveyed, which comprises five families, have an approximate monthly income of PHP 20,001–30,000. Fifth are the 1.21% of the fathers from the total families surveyed, which comprise two families with a respective approximate monthly income of PHP 30,001 and above. Last is that 29.69% of the fathers in the total population surveyed, which comprises 49 families, do not have a monthly income. The column also shows that the majority of the fathers from the families surveyed in Barangay Pantihan II have an approximate monthly income of PHP 5,000 and below. The least number of fathers from the surveyed families have an approximate monthly income of PHP 30,001 and above.

Meanwhile, 45.46% of the mothers from the total families surveyed, which comprises the 75 families in Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite, have a monthly income of PHP 5,000 and below. Second is the 5.45% of the mothers from the total families surveyed, which comprises nine families with an approximate monthly income of PHP 5,001–10,000. Third, 1.81% of the mothers from the total families surveyed, which comprise the three families, have an approximate monthly income of PHP 10,001–20,000. Fourth, 0.6% of the mothers from the total families surveyed, which comprise one family, have an approximate monthly income of PHP 20,001–30,000. Fifth, none of the mothers from the total families surveyed have a respective approximate monthly income of PHP 30,001 and above. Last are the 46.67% of the mothers in the total population surveyed, which comprises 77 families that do not have a monthly income. The column shows that the majority of the mothers from the families surveyed in Barangay Pantihan II do not have a monthly income. The least number of mothers from the surveyed families have an approximate monthly income of PHP 20,001 and above.

On the other hand, 13.33% of the other family members from the total families surveyed, which comprises 22 families in Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite, have a monthly income of PHP 5,000 and below. Second are 7.27% of the other family members from the total families surveyed, which comprises 12 families with an approximate monthly income of PHP 5,001–10,000. Third, 4.24% of the other family members from the total families surveyed, which comprise the seven families, have an approximate monthly income of PHP 10,001–20,000. Fourth, 3.03% of the other family members from the total families surveyed, which comprises five families, have an approximate monthly income of PHP 20,001–30,000. Fifth, 1.21% of the other family members from the total families surveyed have a respective approximate monthly income of PHP 30,001 and above. Last are 46.67% of the other family members from the total population surveyed, which comprises 77 people who do not have a monthly income. The column shows that the majority of the mothers from the families surveyed in Barangay Pantihan II do not have a monthly income. The least number of mothers from the surveyed families have an approximate monthly income of PHP 30,001 and above.

Table 11. Lot and home ownership (n = 165)

Ownership	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Lot ownership	Yes	91	55.15%
	No	74	44.85%
Home ownership	Yes	138	83.64%
	No	27	16.36%

The residents of Barangay Pantihan II have a split who owns their lot at 55% while those who did not were 45%. Meanwhile, in home ownership 84% or the majority says they have home ownership and 16% who do not have. This finding is similar with the study of Li (2015) as Generation Y people were considering home ownership due to related government policies, while Generation X were concerned on the quality of life.

Table 12. Kind of neighborhood (n = 165)

Type of family	Frequency	Percentage
Close relationship	160	96.97%
With conflicts	5	3.03%

This table presents the kind of neighborhood in their households. 160 of the respondents have a close relationship with their neighborhood, and the other five respondents answered that they have conflicts instead. This result implies that most families like to have associations with their neighbors in getting to know with one another.

Table 13. Type of materials used (n = 165)

Type of materials used	Frequency	Percentage
Wood	41	24.85%
Concrete	51	30.91%
Mixed	72	43.64%
Makeshift	0	0.00%
Others	1	0.61%

In Table 13, forty-two (42) residents described their house to be made out of wood, 51 residents whose houses were concrete, and 72 residents who said their house was made out of mixed. One family cited other materials used in their homes, while none of them were living in makeshift houses. This shows that some houses have mixed building materials in order to have strong foundation with walling and roofing systems.

Table 14. Distribution of respondents in terms of source of water supply (n = 165)

Type of water supply	Frequency	Percentage
Owned	70	42.42%
Bought	47	28.48%
Shared	43	26.06%
Others	5	3.03%

In Table 14, 70 (42%) out of 166 respondents have their owned source of water supply, and 47 of them (28%) bought their source of water supply, while 44 (27%) of the respondents shared their source of water supply to the barangay’s water tank. Five (3%) of the respondents get their water supply in the deep wells. This means that the supply of water has become essential in their households.

Figure 1. Distribution of respondents in terms of waste disposal (n = 165)

The chart above shows the waste disposal of the respondents and flush is the highest number of answers with a total of 85, followed by the water-scaled with a total number of 67 and the least number of answers is others with one respondent.

Figure 2. Distribution of respondents in terms of garbage disposal (n = 165)

The highest number of answers according to 165 respondents is burning of garbage with a total of 70. This is followed by waste segregation and both of waste segregation and collecting. Throwing in the river is one of the least answers by the respondents of Brgy. Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite.

Table 15. Hazard materials (n = 165)

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	23	13.94%
No	142	86.06%

In Table 14, it shows in the chart that 86% or 142 of the residents of Pantihan II has no hazardous materials in their houses, while 42% or 23 residents has some hazardous materials that can be found at home such as air fresheners, motor oils, and cleaners. As most of the families do not use hazardous materials found in their households, members should be careful in proper waste disposal or else, it could result in danger.

Figure 3. Foods eaten during breakfast (n = 165)

Twenty-eight percent (28%) of the Barangay Pantihan II residents prefer to eat rice during breakfast. 13% is fish, followed by 11% bread, 9% coffee, and the rest is seldomly eaten as the graph indicates.

Figure 4. Foods eaten during lunch (n = 165)

Similar with breakfast, 36% of the study population eat rice followed by vegetables at 31% and fish at 25%.

Figure 5. Foods eaten during dinner (n = 165)

Rice is the staple food from Pantihan II as indicated in the graph. 35% of the residents eat rice followed again by vegetables at 30% and then fish at 25%. This shows that of all the figures mentioning about meals, rice is generally eaten by most of the households.

Table 16. Distribution of respondents in terms of containers, drinking water storage, and drainage systems (n = 165)

Types		Frequency	Percentage
Containers	Plastic pitchers	95	57.58%
	Bottles	36	21.81%
	Jars and pots	12	7.27%
	Others	22	13.33%
Drinking water storage	Covered	103	62.42%
	Refrigerated	50	30.30%
	Uncovered	12	7.27%
Drainage systems	Open	132	80.00%
	Closed	33	20.00%

In terms of container used 95 (58%) out of 165 respondents used plastic pitchers for their containers and 36 (22%) of them were using bottles, while 12 (7%) said that they are using jars and pots and lastly 22 (13%) are currently using others like water jugs. In terms of drinking water storage, 103 (62%) out of 165 respondents have covers on water storage while 50 (30%) of the respondents have their own refrigerator, and 12 (7%) have their drinking water storage uncovered. On the other hand, there were 132 respondents (80%) who were currently using open type of drainage system according to the ordinance of their municipality while the remaining 33 respondents (20%) were using a closed type of drainage system.

Table 17. Birth deliveries of mothers (n = 165)

Delivery		Frequency	Percentage
Type of delivery	Normal spontaneous delivery	140	84.85%
	Cesarean section	25	15.15%
Location of previous deliveries	Hospital	47	28.48%
	Lying-in clinic	8	4.84%
	Home	80	48.48%
	Both home and hospital	30	18.18%

In terms of type of delivery, 85% of all the mothers in Pantihan II delivered their babies through normal spontaneous delivery while the 15% delivered their babies through Cesarean section. In terms of location where mothers labored, 42% of the mothers in Pantihan II gave birth at their homes. 28% gave birth in the hospitals, 18% gave birth both at home and at the hospital, and 4% gave birth in a lying-in clinic.

Figure 6. Common illness (Father)

This figure represents the total number of illness in the father’s side. Majority of the fathers who have not had illness. Some of them still experienced coughs and colds. The following illnesses also showed low percentages, so in all illnesses cough and colds are the highest (if not counting those who do not experience such illnesses).

Figure 7. Common illness (Mother)

Neck pain, allergies, physical accident, asthma, body weakness, and headache are ranged 1% at the community. The 2% goes for the urinary tract infection (UTI) as it is unusual for them to have that kind of illness. As for the 7% fever and hypertension are somehow common in the area: hypertension due to the lifestyle and fever happens to the mothers because of uncertain circumstances of their daily living. Most of them had experienced cough and colds that usually happens during rainy season. Meanwhile, 64% of the mothers in the community did not experience some common illness because they usually eat healthy and exercise daily, as their exercises are usually their tasks on their everyday chores.

Table 18. Common illness (Children) (n = 214)

Common illness (Children)	Frequency	Percentage
Abdominal pain	1	0.47%
Asthma	1	0.47%
Colds	3	1.40%
Cough	52	24.30%
Diarrhea	50	23.36%
Fatigue	2	0.93%
Fever	1	0.47%
Flu	37	17.29%
Headache	4	1.87%
Hypertension	2	0.93%
Inguinal hernia	1	0.47%
Low hemoglobin	1	0.47%
Rashes	2	0.93%
Sore eyes	2	0.93%
Sore throat	1	0.47%
Stomach pain	1	0.47%
Tonsilitis	1	0.47%
Toothache	1	0.47%
Urinary tract infection (UTI)	3	1.40%
None	47	21.96%

According to the scale, most children respondents in Pantihan II have experienced coughs with 24.30%, followed by diarrhea with 23.36%, and flu with 17.29%. Each of the respondents also encountered illnesses such as abdominal pain, asthma, inguinal hernia, low hemoglobin, sore throat, stomach pain, tonsilitis, and toothache. Some children have not come across with different illnesses (21.96%).

Figure 8. Distribution of respondents in terms of environmental facilities

In terms of environmental facilities, majority of the respondents that researchers surveyed answered that their resources and facilities are functional, but there are two of the respondents that answered that it is not functional.

Figure 9. Distribution of respondents in terms of consultation

Above is a chart showing the distribution of respondents in terms of consultation preference ranging from 1-8. 1 (folk massage therapists or manghihilot), 2 (Midwife), 3 (Doctor), 4 (Barangay Health Worker), 5 (Albaryo), 6 (Nurse), 7 (Health center), 8 (Others), and a variety of consultation preference follows. Respondents prefer to have their consultation in the health center with a staggering 30.90% of the total survey, followed by consultation with the doctor at 23.03% and placing 3 is a variety of a doctor and the health center at 11.51%, Respondents still consult folk massage therapists (manghihilot) with 4.84%, while barangay health workers (BHWs) have 1.21%. The rest of the data are at 2.42%, 1.81%, and 0.60%.

Figure 10. Distribution of respondents in terms of other consultations

The highest number is the number one which represents the most consult person for problems other than health. The least or nothing are the numbers 1, 4, and 5. It seems that family is the most trusted person whom you can talk for problems other than health, among others.

Table 19. Family adequacy (n = 165)

Questions	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Does the family have adequate elimination?	Yes	139	15.76%
	No	26	84.24%
Does the family have adequate exercise?	Yes	32	19.39%
	No	133	80.61%
Does the family have adequate relaxation activities?	Yes	155	93.94%
	No	10	6.06%
Does the family have adequate rest and sleep?	Yes	130	78.79%
	No	35	21.21%
Does the family have stress management activities?	Yes	144	87.27%
	No	21	12.73%

The table shows that on the first question, 84% of the respondents have adequate / good elimination pattern whilst the 16% of the respondents do not. The second question shows that 80.6% of the respondents attain adequate rest and 19.3% do not have adequate rest. The third question shows that 94% of 165 respondents have adequate relaxation activities while the 6% of the respondents do not have adequate relaxation activities. The fourth question shows that 78.79% of 165 respondents have adequate rest and sleep whilst the 21.21% do not. The fifth and final question shows that 87% of 165 total respondents have stress management activities and 13% do not have any. Carroll et al. (2020) reported that some families experience behavior changes and stressors on health and weight-related outcomes, whether positively or negatively.

Figure 11. Distribution of respondents in terms of appliances owned

The highest number of answers in appliances owned is the respondents who own television and electric fan with a total of 50, followed by the respondents who own television, refrigerator, and electric fan with a total of 26 answers. Those least numbers are those respondents who own more than three of different kinds of appliances.

Table 19. Distribution of respondents in terms of breeding sites and pets kept at home (n = 165)

Distribution	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Breeding sites of insects and rodents	Yes	122	73.94%
	No	43	26.06%
Pets / animals kept at home	Yes	147	89.09%
	No	18	10.91%

It shows in this table that 73.94% or 122 of the residents in the community has breeding sites of insects and rodents, and the rest with 26.06% or 43 do not have any. Furthermore, 89.09% or 147 of the residents have pets or animals at their houses, and 19.90% or 18 residents do not have any.

Conclusion

Community health assessment (or community health profile) helps researchers, especially in the nursing profession, determine the strengths of the community and the improvements that are needed for a positive change. Through the implementation of the initiatives, community health nurses actively cooperate with individuals, community organizations, health facilities, and local governments to achieve the goals and outcomes of the community itself.

The study explored socio-economic factors in Barangay Pantihan II, Maragondon, Cavite. Results discovered about disposals, birth deliveries, adequacies, illnesses, and other functions that can be related or connected in their respective households. Barangay leaders and stakeholders from St. Dominic College of Asia must plan and implement steps to address the needs and problems of the community, particularly in a specific barangay. Higher education institutions must include the needs and problems identified in this study as part of their component in conducting community activities such as outreach programs.

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